

A Study of Manganese(II) Complex of Fluorescein. Part IV.

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Studies in Mn(II) complex of fluorescein are in continuation of the report of the author on Cu(II), Fe(II), Fe(III) and vanadyl(IV) complexes of the same ligand. Here the exchange interaction between two manganese ions is discussed and spin-free spin-paired equilibrium established in the complex.

THIS author has published his work¹⁻³ on the complexes of Cu(II), Fe(II), Fe(III) and rare earth complexes of fluorescein. The detailed findings of vanadyl(IV) complex of the ligand are reported in a separate communication⁴. Mn(II) is an interesting ion since in a weak octahedral field the ground state is $(t_{2g})^3(e_g)^2$ with five unpaired spin and a magnetic moment of 5.92 B.M., whereas in the strong field limit it assumes $(t_{2g})^5$ configuration with only one unpaired spin. This paper deals with magnetic, spectral and electrical properties of Mn(II) complex of fluorescein as a continuation of the work already reported¹⁻³.

Experimental

Preparation of the metal complex

Manganese(II) fluorescein complex was precipitated as a reddish brown precipitate by adding 100 ml of 0.05M alcoholic solution of fluorescein to 100 ml of 0.05M MnCl₂ solution with continuous stirring. The pH was adjusted between 5.8 to 6.2. The precipitate was made free from impurities and dried at 80°.

Analysis :	C	H	Mn
Found	53.42	4.45	13.06
Calculated for Mn ₂ C ₄₀ H ₃₁ O ₁₇	53.54	4.02	12.37

The complex was insoluble in all normal solvents. Magnetic, spectral (electronic absorption and infrared) measurements were done as described in a previous communication¹. 5 cm path cell was used in the spectral measurements.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 records the electronic absorption spectrum of Mn(II) complex of fluorescein with probable assignment given in the last column.

The solid reflectance band at 24,630 cm⁻¹ and the solution band at 23,980 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$, 4E transition and the band at 18,080

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION SPECTRUM OF Mn₂C₄₀H₃₄O₁₇

	$\bar{\nu}$, cm ⁻¹	ϵ (molar)	Assignment
Solid, Diffuse reflectance.	24,630	—	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$, 4E
	23,980	0.6	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$, 4E
Solution 2.42 × 10 ⁻¹ M in D.M.F.	18,080	0.03	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$

cm⁻¹ to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transition on the basis of assignment of absorption bands⁵ for Mn(H₂O)₆²⁺ and the observation that the lowest electronic transition occur at higher energies with free water molecule as a ligand than most other ligands. The low values of extinction coefficient lend support to the contention that they are probably spin-forbidden d-d bands.

The two bands ~24,000 cm⁻¹ and ~18,000 cm⁻¹ give the best fit at Dq/B = 1.7 in the Tanabe-Sugano diagram for d⁵ configuration. From the diagram,

$$[{}^4A_{1g}, {}^4E \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}]/B = 33 = \frac{24,000}{B}$$

Hence, for Mn(II) complex B ~ 730 cm⁻¹, Dq ~ 1250 cm⁻¹ and nephelauxetic ratio $\beta = 0.66$. The mean pairing energy is calculated from Jorgensen's relation⁶, $\pi \sim 7.5B + 4C \sim 27.5B$ which gives $\pi \sim 20,000$ cm⁻¹. The values obtained may not be valid if an equilibrium mixture of the two spin states of the Mn(II) complex is supposed to be existing.

The infrared spectral pattern (Table 2) of the manganese(II) complex of fluorescein indicates that the metal ligand coordination takes place through either -OH or C-O or both. The significant shifts of infrared frequencies assigned to -OH and C-O groups in fluorescein is a proof that the coordination is taking place through these positions. The frequency at 1175 cm⁻¹ and at 1090 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to hydroxy bridges and M-OH frequencies in polynuclear complexes¹.

The variation of magnetic susceptibility with temperature (Table 3) appears to follow the Curie-Weiss behaviour upto the room temperature and then

TABLE 2—INFRARED DATA FOR $Mn_2C_{40}H_{34}O_{71}$

$Mn_2C_{40}H_{34}O_{71}$	Fluorescein, the ligand	
Wave number, cm^{-1}	Wave number, cm^{-1}	Assignment
1090*	705	
	755	
1175(hydroxy bridges)	920	associated carboxyl group.
1270	1235	C—O stretching.
1320	1375	O—H deformation
1600	1588	aromatic ring
1625	1625	antisymmetric COO— stretching.
3450	1500—3500	

* Assigned to M—OH frequencies in polynuclear complexes.

deviates. The magnetic moments vary between 3.53 B.M. at 83°K and 4.85 B.M. at 404°K. It neither corresponds to spin only magnetic moment of Mn(II) nor to $(t_{2g})^5$ configuration with a magnetic moment of 1.79 B.M.

By using the expression of Figgis⁷, namely,

$$\chi_A = \frac{\chi {}^6A_{1g} + \chi {}^2T_{2g}E - (E {}^2T_{2g} - E {}^6A_{1g})/kT}{1 + E - (E {}^2T_{2g} - E {}^6A_{1g})/kT}$$

the difference in the energies of the ${}^2T_{2g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g}$ ground terms were obtained for the Mn(II) complex. These are given in Table 3, alongside the χ_M values of the complex at different temperatures. The data indicate that at higher temperatures the spin-free state appears to be of lower energy. At other temperatures the spin-paired state is relatively more stable.

 TABLE 3— $E_2T_{2g} - E_6A_{1g}$ VALUES AND kT VALUES IN cm^{-1}

$T^\circ(k)$	$\chi_M \times 10^6$ c.g.s.	$E_2T_{2g} - E_6A_{1g}$	kT
83	18805	— 56.1	56.5
182	9780	— 96.0	125
217	8596	— 95.2	148
302	7005	— 84.5	206
331	7100	— 27.5	224
344	6980	— 14.0	235
362	6695	— 9.6	244
380	6536	+ 9.1	259
389	6630	+ 34.4	266
404	7215	+ 151.8	274

a) The values of ${}^6A_{1g}$ was calculated from the magnetic moment values of 5.9 B.M.

b) spin-orbit coupling constant was taken to be 300 cm^{-1} .

In order to investigate whether there is an equilibrium of mixture of two spin states in the manganese (II) complex studied, method adopted by Stoufer and coworkers⁸ was applied and the mole fraction of spin-paired and spin free state of the complex calculated. These are given in Table 4. The data are used to evaluate the energy of activation of such an equilibrium. The plots of $\log K_{eq}$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 1) fall fairly well on a straight line except at temperatures above 90°. The energy of activation comes

out to be 0.258 Kcals/mole which confirms that an equilibrium between spin-paired and spin-free states of Mn(II) does exist to a degree though the equilibrium seems to be feeble.

 TABLE 4—DATA FOR SPIN-PAIRED, SPIN-FREE EQUILIBRIUM IN THE COMPLEX $Mn_2C_{40}H_{34}O_{71}$

$T^\circ(k)$	Mole fraction spin-paired	Mole fraction spin-free	K_{eq}
83	0.732	0.268	2.73
147	0.730	0.270	2.71
182	0.716	0.284	2.52
217	0.685	0.315	2.18
287	0.613	0.387	1.59
302	0.634	0.366	1.73
331	0.568	0.432	1.31
344	0.543	0.457	1.19
362	0.539	0.461	1.17
380	0.519	0.481	1.08
389	0.517	0.483	1.07

The magnetic moment 4.13 B.M. of the Mn(II) complex at 302°K is fairly close to the room temperature value 3.87 B.M. expected for a configuration with partial spin-pairing having the ground state term ${}^4A_{1g}(b_{2g}^2e_g^2a_{1g}^1)$ in a square planar stereochemistry⁹.

Fig. 1

The experimental magnetic moment of the complex may be attributed to partial spin-pairing with some orbital contribution introduced by spin-orbit coupling with higher terms which could raise the magnetic moment to the observed value.

In order to test whether the observed magnetic behaviour of the manganese(II) complex could be explained by invoking exchange interaction between two manganese ions, the method adopted by Earnshaw¹⁰ *et al.* was adopted. Table 5 gives the value of kT/J , μ (theoretical) and μ (observed) calculated according to the method cited above. It is found that it is possible to fit the experimental results with the theoretical ones at least in part

and hence permit a positive, though not very firm, conclusion regarding magnetic exchange between neighbouring ions.

bridges and its low magnetic moments which may be considered as an indirect proof of metal-metal bond.

TABLE 5— kT/J , (THEORETICAL) AND (OBS.) VALUES ACCORDING TO EARNshaw¹⁰ *et al.*

kT/J	(Theoretical) μ (B.M.)	(Observed) μ (B.M.)
3.94	2.72	3.62
5.17	3.26	3.70
6.35	3.58	3.78
7.58	3.75	3.88
8.70	3.94	3.97
10.06	4.18	4.05
11.55	4.28	4.13
11.32	4.28	4.25
11.52	4.34	4.35
11.90	4.40	4.40
12.65	4.40	4.42
13.60	4.46	4.48
14.10	4.62	4.85

It may be concluded that the manganese(II) complex of fluorescein can be assigned a structure: $Mn_2(FlFn)_2(OH)_4(H_2O)_4$ (flcn = fluorescein anion) which satisfies, in part, its polymeric nature, hydroxy

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